

Romanian-Turkey Politico-Diplomatic Relations (1971-1974)

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ABSTRACT: The stage of the relations between Romania and Turkey, at the political-diplomatic level, has seen an ascending development as a result of the high level visits, thus laying the foundations of the formation of friendship groups within the two parliaments, contact and mutual visits at the level of the ministers, of municipalities. There was, however, a moment of stagnation, which was not a particular feature but a general feature that manifested itself both in Turkey's external relations and in domestic political life, with the formation of the Naim Talu government, a transitional government. It could engage in large-scale external relation sanctions. The Turkish press as well as the diplomatic environment expressed interest in learning about the concrete problems, addressing Romanian diplomats in Ankara, the Czechoslovak ambassador, the adviser of the U.S. Embassy, the ambassadors of Bulgaria and Greece and one of the advisers of the R.F. German embassy.

KEYWORDS: politician, diplomat, official visit, parliamentary group

Introduction

At the invitation of the Turkish Government, the Romanian Minister of Foreign Affairs, Corneliu Mănescu, paid an official visit to Turkey, on November 3-7, 1971 (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1971, TURKEY 5, Vol. 2, telegram no. 12.484 / 04.11.1971, addressed to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, f. 1). In the talks with the Prime Minister, Nihat Erim and the Foreign Minister, Osmat Olcay, the following issues were mainly addressed:

Regarding the bilateral relations, it was reaffirmed the wish of the Romanian party to expand and diversify on multiple levels the Romanian-Turkish relations, highlighting the possibilities existing in the economic, cultural, technical-scientific fields, etc.

Turkish interlocutors expressed interest in amplifying bilateral relations. Prime Minister Nihat Erim stressed the need to continue contacts with the leaders of the two governments.

Regarding the concrete forms of expanding trade and technical-economic cooperation, it was agreed that at the second session of the Romanian-Turkish Joint Economic Commission, the modalities of exploiting the existing possibilities could be addressed.

It was also established that the negotiations for the conclusion of the commercial protocol between April 1, 1972- March 31, 1973, would take place in Bucharest, in the second half of February 1972, following that the protocol would enter into force on April 1, 1972. The Turkish officials had generally a favorable attitude for granting licenses for the import and export goods provided in the current list. It is significant that on the eve of the visit was granted a license to export to Romania half of the quantity of cotton provided in the commercial protocol (1500 tones). At the same time, Turkish representatives insisted on the positive resolution of the demand for imported goods (petroleum products and chemical fertilizers) as well as on the Turkish tobacco export operation against Romanian cars and machines. (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1971, TURKEY 5, Vol. 2, note MAE, direction I Relations, no. 01/010401).

From the discussions resulted the interest of Turkey in constructing an assembly line for the 50 hp tractor, if the Romanian side could offer the 40-45 hp tractor, as well as for the cooperation in the production of parts and subassemblies for the Renault 12 (Dacia 1300), which is mounted in Romania and Turkey.

The two foreign ministers pointed out the existence of new possibilities for developing cultural-scientific exchanges, appreciating the usefulness of continuing in 1972 the contacts at government level on the line of ministries of education (education) and health.

As a conclusion of the visit for the talks between the two foreign ministers regarding the political relations were appreciated by the two parties: setting up friendship groups within the two parliaments, contacts and mutual visits between the ministers of culture and national education, representatives foreign ministers, mayors of the two capitals, representatives of the ministries of tourism, the first session of the Romanian-Turkish Joint Economic Commission and the preparations for the second session to take place, the entry into force in September 1971 of the agreement regulating scientific exchanges and artistic.

At the level of 1972, as a general appreciation made on the evolution of the Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations, it can be considered that they marked a normal evolution, and the visit to Turkey of the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Romania, its reception by President Cevdet Sunay and the first Minister Nihat Erim, the talks at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs highlighted real possibilities for further development of bilateral relations.

On the occasion of the meeting held on January 7, 1972, between Romanian diplomats and President Sunay, Prime Minister Nihat Erim and Foreign Minister H. Bayulken expressed their wish, “to do everything to develop relations with our country” (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1972, File 2352, f. 12).

The agreed actions envisaged on the agenda of bilateral relations for 1972 were: continuation of contacts and exchanges of visits on parliamentary line (meetings between representatives of friendship groups and foreign policy commissions), governmental (visit to Turkey of the Romanian education minister, for Turkey to know the system of organization and efficiency of higher education in Romania as well as the visits in Romania of the ministers of tourism and health in Turkey).

Regarding the economic relations, the actions envisaged were: the negotiation of the protocol of trade exchanges and the meeting of the joint commission of economic cooperation. Regarding the high level contacts and on the line of the foreign ministries, the planned actions were the visit of the minister of foreign affairs H. Bayulken, in Romania, in response to the visit undertaken in November 1971 by the Romanian minister, Corneliu Mănescu.

As an example, the visit of the first deputy foreign minister, George Macoveanu, to Turkey in October 11-16, 1972, to continue contacts and exchange of views between the two ministries on issues of common interest: bilateral issues, cooperation Balkan and other international issues. This is because, during the visit of the Romanian Minister of Foreign Affairs, Corneliu Mănescu, it was agreed to ensure the continuity of the meetings on the line of the foreign ministries.

On the occasion of the visit, the Romanian party expressed its desire “to continue the bilateral contacts at governmental level, on the line of the ministries of foreign, health, tourism, education and education, as well as on the parliamentary line” (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1972, File 2354, f.10).

Also at the level of bilateral relations, the desire of the Romanian party to establish contacts on the front line of the Socialist Unity in Romania and of the main political parties in Turkey was specified: the Justice Party and the People’s Republican Party. At the same time, the Romanian side would be sensitive if the Turkish authorities would allow the name of the Romanian capital to be given a street in Ankara (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1972, File 2354, telegram 012.604 / 02.09.1972, f. 19.). At the same time, the Romanian side expressed its satisfaction with raising the level of representation of the two parties in the Romanian-Turkish economic joint commission but also on the need to facilitate the normal conduct of trade - the Turkish side issuing import and export licenses for the goods stipulated in the Commercial Protocol signed in Bucharest, in February 1972.

It was also noted the usefulness of signing a two-year cultural and scientific exchange program, for the application of the cultural and scientific exchange agreement concluded in 1966, and as a more urgent problem it was mentioned the interest of the Romanian party that more

specialists in turcology receive the permission of to study documents related to the history of Romania, located in the Turkish archives or the Turkish language and literature.

Regarding consular relations, the ratification of the Convention on Legal Assistance in Civil and Criminal Matters signed in 1968, as well as the need for ratification and the Consular Convention signed in the same year, was appreciated by the Turkish side.

Regarding the Balkan cooperation, the possibility of meeting of the foreign ministers from the Balkan countries was discussed, which together would examine the possibilities of peaceful co-operation and continuous improvement of the relations between the states in the area. A second objective was to sign a joint document reflecting the desire of the people of the Balkans to live in peace and good neighborliness (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1972, File 2354, f. 15). At the level of 1973, On the occasion of the high level meeting between the Deputy Minister, Nicolae Ecobescu and the Turkish Ambassador to Bucharest, Osman Derinsu, from January 31, 1973, the Romanian diplomat revealed the Romanian side's desire to further develop relations with Turkey in all areas. He also stressed the need for increased joint efforts to develop economic exchanges between the two countries that were not at the level of possibilities. Nicolae Ecobescu also referred to the possibilities for collaboration between the two countries in terms of promoting cooperation in the Balkans (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3971, telegram no. 01./0962/31.01.1973).

In his turn, the Turkish ambassador expressed the wish to contribute to the development of the Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations and to support the cooperation between the two countries in international issues of common interest.

Also after the high level talks, on April 25, 1973, Suleyman Demirel, the president of the Justice Party, explained that “in the development of bilateral relations a certain more difficult period has occurred in the last two years”, but “this is not a particular feature of the Romanian-Turkish relations, but a general feature that has manifested itself both in Turkey's external relations and in domestic political life”. His opinion was that, with the formation of the Naim Talu government, “a new stage in life was passed Turkey's internal stage, although it was a transitional government, which could not engage in large-scale external relations actions, but the Justice Party assumed a new responsibility, through the large number of ministers, (almost half) from the leadership of the party) in the idea of preparing conditions for the post-election period when we plan to form the government alone (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3966, telegram no. 012660 / 25.04.1973, f. 16).

At the end of the talks, S. Demirel expressed the conviction that “there will be beautiful days” for Romanian-Turkish relations, especially that between Romania and Turkey, although countries with different social horizons, there is no litigious or pending issue (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3966, telegram no. 012660 / 25.04.1973, f. 17). He also stated that “the most suitable ways to perform mutually beneficial actions in the field of oil industry, construction of agricultural machines, possibly tractors, chemical industry” must be found. (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3966, telegram no. 012660 / 25.04.1973, f. 17).

On the occasion of the reception offered by the President of Turkey, F. Koruturk, for the heads of the diplomatic missions accredited in Ankara, on June 15, 1972, regarding the contacts that have taken place in recent years between the heads of the two states, as well as at other levels, the Romanian diplomats. They remarked, “that they had an important place in the development of the relations of friendship and cooperation between Romania and Turkey and are prospects to know a new development” (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3966, telegram no. 012381/15.06.1973).

On August 22, 1972, during a visit to the Secretary General of the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ismail Erez, Romanian diplomats expressed their desire, “to extend the political contacts between the two countries, as well as on the line of the two foreign ministries. but also the fact that the Romanian Ministry of Foreign Affairs is willing to continue the exchanges of views initiated in 1970 and, in general, to maintain good contacts with the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Affairs for exchanges of views and information regarding the development of bilateral

relations and in relation to some international problems - European security, military disengagement in Europe, problems of Balkan cooperation, etc.” (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3966, telegram no. 012504 / 22.08.1973).

At the level of 1974, the desire of the Romanian party to develop relations with Turkey in all areas was expressed on the occasion of the meeting between Nicolae Ecobescu, Deputy Foreign Minister and O. Derinsu, Turkish Ambassador to Bucharest, on January 31, 1973. The Romanian Minister, emphasized the need to make greater joint efforts to develop economic exchanges between the two countries that do not rise to the level of possibilities, “the Romanian Minister also referred to the possibilities existing in terms of collaboration between the two countries, on the plan to promote cooperation in the Balkans, “O. Derinsu, in turn”, expressed the wish to contribute to the development of the Romanian-Turkish bilateral relations and to support the collaboration between the two countries in international issues of common interest (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3971, telegram no. 01./0962/31.01.1973).

The Romanian-Turkish relations registered a slight stagnation during the period 1972-1973, a fact also reported by Suleyman Demirel, who showed that “in the development of bilateral relations there has been a more difficult period in the last two years, a situation that is not a particular feature of the Romanian-Turkish relations, but a general feature that has manifested itself both in the field of Turkey's external relations and in domestic political life (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3971, telegram no. 012260 / 24.04.1973, f. 16).

Suleyman Demirel's views were that, with the formation of the government, Naim Talu has moved to a new stage in Turkey's domestic life, a stage in which though it is a transitional government, which could not engage in large-scale actions External relations, the Justice Party assumed a certain responsibility, by the large number of ministers (almost half of the party leadership) putting its mark on it, in the idea of preparing conditions for the post-election period, when the government will form itself.

Suleyman Demirel expressed the conviction that “good days will come” for Romanian-Turkish relations, especially since Romania and Turkey - although countries with different social systems, there is no litigation or suspension issue. He also stated that among the socialist countries, Romania occupies a special place, as a result of its extremely active policy, promoted by its leaders, and regarding the bilateral relations some preparations must be started: “to study and to agree later, the ways more suitable for performing mutually advantageous collaborative actions, page 196 (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3971, telegram no. 012260 / 24.04.1973, f. 17). He referred to for example in the field of the oil industry, the construction of agricultural machines, possibly tractors the chemical industry. However, he said, “It is necessary to have patience, the problems to be gradually addressed, to study as carefully as possible, to find those who respond to the highest degree of mutual interest”. He also promised that he will consult with his colleagues, “so that three or four members of the party, possibly, deputies, senators, will pay a visit to Romania, after the parliament will go on vacation, that is after June 15” (AMAE, Turkey fund 1971, issue 220/1973, File 3971, telegram no. 012260 / 24.04.1973, f. 18).

As a synthesis of the state of relations between Romania and Turkey, at the political-diplomatic level, it is that in the last years, the political-diplomatic relations have undergone an ascending development.

A special role in deepening relations between the two countries was the official visit to Turkey in March 1969 by the President of the State Council N. Ceausescu and the official visit to Romania, in April 1970, by the President of the Republic of Turkey.

The exchange of visits between the two heads of state - which was preceded by mutual visits of the first ministers, foreign ministers, representatives of parliaments - gave impetus to the development of contacts between Romania and Turkey, at the governmental level, on the parliamentary line, between municipalities etc.

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